

MAIN DIRECTIONS OF DEVELOPMENT OF ART AND CREATIVITY OF CHILDREN

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Abstract. *In the art classes for young children, children mainly do practical work, tell stories based on works of art, and at school they get more deeply acquainted with such types of fine arts as color image, graphics, sculpture, arts and crafts. Young children have a variety of visual activities: drawing, plasticine, appliqué, design are considered. Great importance is attached to all activities given to young children. The successful solution of educational problems in the primary grades is organically carried out with the figurative activities carried out by young children.*

Keywords: *environment, process, formation, factor, concept, habit, imagination, worldview, thinking, communication.*

The role of the educator in shaping the aesthetic abilities of children through visual activity in young children is incomparable. He should have in-depth knowledge and high qualifications, for this he should regularly work on himself, constantly raise his scientific theoretical level, rely on advanced experiences.

Teaching drawing in pre-school organizations starts at the age of 3. This period is the period of preparing children for visual activities. During this period, children learn to hold a pencil and write on paper. But it does not develop in this process, the child does not know how to hold the pencil correctly, the educator slowly gets used to holding it correctly, the child is interested in the movement of the pencil when it hits the paper with its tip, not what he is doing. He draws various lines and dots with a pencil, makes various movements on the paper surface, and then the simple lines gradually become more complex. At this time, the child will be happy to see different traces on the paper. Therefore, this period is called "Ala - Buji" period. This period has an impact on the creation of visual activity in the child. In this group, the pre-school educational program does not require group activities, but if the children want, they can sit around the table and draw pictures.

In early age groups, children can be given pencils from the age of one and a half. But the understanding of the descriptive meaning of children's actions begins with a small group.

By this period, his speech grows, his imagination expands, and his independent movement with materials becomes active. In this group, the educator teaches children to observe their actions. With the different lines he draws, he teaches to know the types of objects, to compare them to certain things. He asks the children questions, asking the child what you drew, he asks a lot of questions to find out what object the child drew is similar to. The child's movements are involuntary.

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pencil and write on paper. But it does not develop in this process, the child does not know how to hold the pencil correctly, the educator slowly gets used to holding it correctly, the child is interested not in what he is doing, but in the movement of the pencil when he taps the paper with its tip. He draws various lines and dots with a pencil, makes various movements on the paper surface, and then the simple lines gradually become more complex. At this time, the child will be happy to see different traces on the paper. Therefore, this period is called "Ala - Buji" period. This period has an impact on the creation of visual activity in the child. In this group, although the preschool education program does not require group activities, if the children want, they can be allowed to sit around the table and draw pictures.

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By this period, his speech grows, his imagination expands, and his independent movement with materials becomes active. In this group, the teacher teaches children to observe their actions. He teaches to know the types of objects by drawing different lines, to compare them to certain things. He asks the children questions, asking him what did you draw, he asks many questions that determine what object the child drew. The child's movements are involuntary.

Not all children can identify the similarity between the objects in the work created as a result of their actions at the same time, the growth of this feature causes the development of speech by itself. They describe simple objects and events in the work of our educators. For example: It is raining, snowing, leaves are flying, water is flowing in the river, etc. Children's interest in colors gradually increases in 3 years. They use different colors to make it look like an object.

For example: a small piece of paper is painted in red and says "I planted flowers". In this group, the teacher draws the children some part of the subject and offers to complete it. For example: string to a balloon, stick to a flag, and learn to know and use red, green, blue, yellow colors. "Sun", "blue grass", "flowers". At first, children draw with a pencil, after 3-4 sessions they paint using paint, and are taught how to use it. Children can draw pictures with paints on the following topics. For example: The leaves are falling from the trees, "the lights are on in the house." In the 2nd half of the year, the teacher teaches children to describe the subject in a simple way.

The teacher draws a balloon, the children, the teacher draws a ball - the children are on their way. In the 2nd half of the year, children will be trained to decorate a doll's shirt or a napkin and gloves with spots. Educators use different methods to teach children of this age how to draw.

One of the methods for quality teaching is the method of passive actions, that is, the child acts independently. The teacher hands the child a pencil and performs drawing actions or plays a game. As children develop the coordination of hand movements, the educator performs the same rhythmic movements on the paper, then gradually teaches them to perform complex movements from left to right. For example: a coil of thread or smoke coming out, etc.

The teacher's use of artistic words helps children to visualize what is being depicted. For example: the method of using such poems and songs about the sun is considered one of the important methods. In the 1st subgroup, solidarity with foster children is widely used. The teacher draws a Christmas tree on a large sheet of paper, and the children turn on the lights. (by putting the brush on a piece of paper). Such activities can be organized by a teacher with groups of 5-6 children. It is possible to organize type activities with children aged 3.5 years. For example: you can give children pictures and play games like what is depicted in them. For example: sun, flag,

flowers can be depicted. The children tell them, the teacher helps the child in trouble. Analyzing children's work, the educator shows the diversity of their work and the similarity between the subject and the image.

Tasks necessary for the successful completion of school work for young children are solved. In the process of painting, appliqué, and clay works, children's thinking is formed such as analysis, synthesis, repetition, concretization. Also, during these processes, children learn to work in a team, to subordinate their actions to the actions of their peers. Children's activities of visual activity in children of small age form skills necessary in children's educational activities.

The primary direction of visual activity of pre-school education organizations is artistic and aesthetic education of young children.

The effect of this direction becomes clear only when all means of aesthetic direction (theatre, music, fiction, painting, appliqué, etc.) are used in a complex manner. "Illustrative activity" classes for young children are of great importance in solving the problems of aesthetic education for children. Because visual activity is an artistic activity by its nature. All types of artistic activities open wide opportunities for children to know beauty and develop an emotional-aesthetic attitude towards existence.

In the process of "visual activity" training:

1. Education of artistic taste;
2. Development of practical artistic activities and skills;
3. Development of fantasy, creative thinking and imagination, perception;
4. Development of precise hand movements and fine motor skills of fingers;
5. Educational and educational issues, such as creating an opportunity for the budding of professional artistic and creative activity, are solved.

From the analysis of the structure and content of the improved "First Step" state program developed for preschool education organizations, it is clear that, starting with small groups, the most time is allocated to visual activities.

If the types of visual activity

- painting (2 hours),
- application (0.5 hours),
- build-make (0.5 hours)
- If we add clay work (1 hour), the total is 4 hours.

If we take into account that the weekly workload is 12 hours, visual activity makes up one third of all activities. Therefore, visual activity is considered the largest department that acquires integrative content and is carried out in a logical and didactic connection with other types of activity. This factor means that it is necessary to improve the content and methodology of visual activity classes simultaneously with other types of activity.

Children learn to control their character and hand strength, to freely use a pencil and a brush in group art activities. This will help children acquire skills and develop the features of light, free, even movement of their hands. In the process of drawing objects of different shapes, sizes, and proportions, children learn the need to maintain direction depending on the working characteristics of the object, and to move in accordance with the size of the object. In visual activity classes conducted for young children, they learn to use materials in an orderly manner, to keep them clean, but to plan the necessary materials and ways of using them. These activities develop children's attention and visual memory.

Younger children naturally have higher requirements for drawing or painting, and these requirements are closer to school requirements. It is done only at the initial stage of children's preparation and learning in a large group, showing the sequence of work in describing nature. Children try to analyze nature, write down the whole general form on sketch paper, compare the picture with nature, correct mistakes and shortcomings, make it similar to nature.

In visual activities, it is possible to find or see geometric shapes, to call them by terms, to get acquainted with the size of width, length, height, and the spatial location of parts relative to each other.

Building with materials during construction activities develops children's visual perception and helps them master technical lessons at school.

Thus, artistic taste and creative abilities of children grow in visual activity classes, and through this, they prepare for studying at school. Because children are inextricably connected with objects, they get to know their unique qualities, shape, color, size, and determine their differences and similarities, which allows them to educate children sensorially, to think visually and figuratively.

Image activity educates children morally. In their works, children reflect the events that are happening in their lives and society, they are pleased and excited about them. In the process of visual activity, the qualities of the will are brought up in children, such as completing the work that has been started, setting a goal and striving to achieve it, overcoming difficulties, helping one's friends. In the process of creating team work, children are taught qualities such as helping each other, working together, in the process of evaluating work, they have a realistic attitude of their peers to work, correct evaluation, and joy in their work and the work of their peers. such moral qualities are formed.

Visual activity is an activity that encourages children to work tirelessly to achieve their goals. Image activity is considered the main means of providing aesthetic education to children. Distinguishing the size, color, shape, location of each object in space are considered parts of this aesthetic sense. The development of aesthetic sense in children is related to a deeper perception of color and proportion. If a child perceives color, shape, and its variety, he will enjoy and enjoy the diversity of the mixture of colors. The development of aesthetic sense in children develops an aesthetic assessment of the object and some of its qualities. It educates them to understand works of visual art, feelings and attitude towards them. Visual arts play an important role in children's artistic and creative growth.

The artistic and creative growth of a child is considered figurative thinking, aesthetic perception and the acquisition of skills and abilities necessary for image creation. For example: a walk to nature or an amusement park, organizing an excursion in autumn. Educating children through the aesthetic feeling that comes from observing the object or the surroundings, it is possible to educate such qualities as the right appreciation of the environment, people's work, and love for the Motherland.

It is considered the main task of artistic and moral education to make children to do their work more beautifully and well, to be liked by others and happy when they see it.

Visual activity of young children is of great importance. The acquisition of knowledge and skills in painting, clay, construction materials is the basis for successful acquisition of art classes and work classes at school. It prepares them for educational activities: teaches them to listen to the teacher and follow his instructions. One of the main reasons for this educational activity is to find

the main and important ways to solve the task. It also plays a role in controlling one's own work in the process of visual activity and performing tasks at school. Also, the child is psychologically prepared in the process of visual activity.

Activities for the development of creative abilities of young children are of great importance in the formation of a child's personality. All the studies conducted by scientists and psychologists in this field prove that children with creative abilities have a more stable spirit, communicate with them and have a friendly relationship. At a young age, it is recommended to pay special attention to comprehensive development, that is, to the development of literary, artistic and musical abilities of young children. The best way to develop creative skills is through play.

Determining the creative ability of young children

The purpose of the diagnosis is to determine which type of child is more suitable and what kind of imagination he has. This can be done with the help of psychologists who conduct special tests, as a result of which games can be selected to develop the creative abilities of young children. It is also possible to independently determine the capabilities of the child, provide him with various activities and observe the most interesting reasons. Determine what kind of imagination has arisen, it is also possible with behavior in the game. Shows the ability to handle high-level fantasy images, which can be compiled from composite images or subjects. But, regardless of the initial level, the imagination is trained like the muscles of the body - with regular exercises. Young children's musical abilities can and should be developed regardless of their original ability.

Development of creative abilities of high-level preschool teachers

If the creative development of babies occurs through the observation and manipulation of objects, the development of more adult children is carried out through attempts to communicate their feelings through the means available to them. Simply put, the tracking phase moves gradually. that is why development methods and methods are to encourage the child to act. The best part of this century is that it offers children's games in a systematic way that develops the creative abilities of young children.

In particular, there will be classes in the theatrical framework useful for children, because theater activities develop preschoolers in various directions. Children not only learn to complete tasks, participate in theater performances, develop imagination, artistic vision, the ability to perceive the integrity of works, develop the ability to sign. But in this age, the involvement of parents is very important for the development of creative abilities. They should show great interest in the child's activities in the circle and play with him in developing games at home.

Development of artistic and creative abilities of young children

According to the research of psychologists, by the age of three, all children have approximately the same level of artistic ability. Therefore, wait for the child to show a special talent, and then it is not necessary to develop it. A few simple conditions can be observed for each child to develop artistic ability. You need to act at your own pace: at the beginning, to interest the child in drawing, then to show him interest in copying imaginary images, and only after it is clear that he will begin to teach the child the basics of visual arts for deeper reading. to support him. And, of course, do not forget to praise and encourage the baby's activities.

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